

The 2020 Decadal Report and Its Meaning for the NOIRLab User Community

Patrick J. McCarthy
Director, NSF's NOIRLab

In early November of last year, the National Academies released the report of the 2020 Decadal Survey (Figure 1). The report, *Pathways to Discovery in Astronomy and Astrophysics for the 2020s* (hereinafter *Pathways to Discovery*), will shape our field in this decade and beyond. Since the 1960s the decadal surveys have identified key scientific questions and led to the development of major observational facilities. The 4-meter telescopes at Kitt Peak, CTIO, the Gemini 8-meter telescopes, and Vera C. Rubin Observatory all have their origins in decadal surveys.

Figure 1. Cover of the Decadal Survey of Astronomy and Astrophysics (Astro2020) publication. Credit: National Academy of Sciences

Pathways to Discovery lays out an exciting scientific landscape for the decade and an ambitious agenda both on the ground and in space. The science themes identified in the report

— *Worlds and Suns in Context, New Messengers and New Physics, and Cosmic Ecosystems* — span an enormous range of astrophysics and touch on areas ripe for new discoveries. The report builds on these themes to develop three priority science areas: *Pathways to Habitable Worlds, New Windows on the Dynamic Universe, and Unveiling the Drivers of Galaxy Growth*. These in turn drive key areas for investment in capabilities. The portfolio that the report recommends — in space and on the ground, from radio to high energies — has the power to transform our understanding of the Universe and our place in it.

The decadal themes map well to the capabilities currently offered and those under development at NOIRLab and other observatories within the US optical-infrared (OIR) community. The mid-decade launch of Rubin's Legacy Survey of Space and Time (LSST), the deployment of new instruments and adaptive optics systems on the International Gemini Observatory, and the ongoing DOE-, NASA-, and NSF-supported surveys on the 4-meter telescopes all answer the call of the recommendations in *Pathways to Discovery* for studies of the dynamic Universe on large and small scales. The top priority for new ground-based facilities, the US ELT Program, addresses a large fraction of the *Pathways to Discovery* detailed science goals, as noted in the body of the report and in the report's Table K.1.

The US Extremely Large Telescope Program

Many of the key advances in astronomy and astrophysics can be traced to large OIR telescopes on the ground. From Edwin Hubble's discovery of the cosmic expansion to the discovery of the cosmic acceleration, from SNe light curves, and the detection of the extrasolar planets through Doppler spectroscopy, large-aperture telescopes on the ground have driven discovery for centuries. *Pathways to Discovery* makes the case for a *system of extremely large telescopes* — grounded in the Thirty Meter Telescope and the Giant Magellan Telescope.

Those two telescope projects are very advanced in their design and development, and much of the technical risk has

been reduced through years of investment in analysis and prototyping. The road to completion of the telescopes will be long, and there are many issues to resolve. *Pathways to Discovery* presents a set of recommendations that will help the community and agencies navigate the many steps leading to the start of construction. At NOIRLab we look forward to working with the community and the two projects to turn the goals in *Pathways to Discovery* into reality.

The Role of NOIRLab in US Astronomy

The [Report of the Panel on Optical and Infrared Observations from the Ground](#) in appendix K of *Pathways to Discovery* lays out six critical leadership roles for NOIRLab in US astronomy. These include leadership of the US ELT Program, execution of Rubin's LSST, coordination of NOIRLab facilities into a time-domain system, operation of unique capabilities in survey and precision astronomy (e.g., DES, NEID), execution of regular community-based strategic planning exercises, and, lastly, contributions to a healthy program of technical development for astronomical instrumentation. Many of the tasks relating to these roles are well underway; others will require new investments of time and effort along with substantial creativity.

As we head into 2022, we continue to develop the time-domain system with new hardware and software tools. Much of this development is being done in anticipation of the start of Rubin Observatory operations, but there are many

interesting time-domain surveys underway now for which rapid follow-up is essential. New instruments coming to Gemini will help us expand our suite of capabilities offered to the community. *Pathways to Discovery* called for better connectivity between ground- and space-based data archives and for greater attention to pipelines that produce science-ready data and support integrated science platforms. Rubin and Gemini each address this issue: Rubin's science platform will provide a one-stop shop for Rubin data products and connectivity to supporting datasets, while Gemini's DRAGONS software packages will continue to grow and will ultimately replace all of the IRAF-based Gemini tools with modern Python-based pipelines. The work done by the DOE, NOIRLab, and university teams leading the Dark Energy Survey and the Dark Energy Spectroscopic Instrument survey enables a wide range of science. These surveys' tools have broader application and have garnered accolades in the professional software development community. NOIRLab's Community Science and Data Center is our clearinghouse for ground-based data archives and connectivity to archives from space-based observatories. There is much work ahead of us and opportunities for better coordination between ground and space.

The most important, and most challenging, of the roles identified in *Pathways to Discovery* related to strategic planning and technical developments. Now that the report is out and agencies are developing plans, we will engage the community in strategic planning. Topics that we expect to address in 2022 include the US ELTs, adaptive optics, time-domain astronomy,

Figure 2. Virtual meetings have a silver lining. The number and diversity of participants at the 2021 Gemini Science Meeting (GSM) were higher than ever. Those who might not be able to travel to in-person meetings at remote locations can participate virtually. The montage shows a sample of the participants at one session of the 2021 GSM. Credit: International Gemini Observatory/NOIRLab/NSF/AURA

and instrumentation. Naturally, we will continue to support science-focused meetings (Figure 2), as these underpin the community's needs and aspirations. The January AAS meeting was to be our first opportunity to engage the community about *Pathways to Discovery*; we will have to find other channels while the global pandemic remains a force.

Diversity and Inclusion

The 2020 Decadal Survey was the first to include a formal panel on the state of the profession. *Pathways to Discovery* called for greater attention to, and investment in, diversity and inclusion and for demographic data to provide the ability to trace actions to outcomes. *Pathways to Discovery* asked us to “reimagine leadership.”

In 2022 we will implement our dual-anonymous proposal review process. The new proposal development and TAC software support anonymous reviews that include safeguards to protect student thesis projects and other programs that require continuity. Additionally, NOIRLab is sharpening our focus on interactions with our Indigenous communities where our facilities operate and adopting a Community Based Science model as described in the report.

NOIRLab is hiring — into the scientific staff, the engineering teams, and the operations support teams. We are approaching this with an integrated approach to hiring at NOIRLab that aims to build a skilled and diverse workforce — a team of teams driven by values that reflect those of the astronomical community as expressed in *Pathways to Discovery* and other community-derived plans.

In this image it appears as though the telescopes of the Cerro Tololo Inter-American Observatory (CTIO), a Program of NSF's NOIRLab, are growing around the edge of a deep well of stars in this fisheye lens view. Several of the telescopes housed at CTIO are visible around the edge of this image, including (clockwise from the top): the SMARTS 0.9-meter Telescope, the SMARTS 1.5-meter Telescope, the Víctor M. Blanco 4-meter Telescope, the Curtis Schmidt Telescope, the SMARTS 1.0-meter Telescope and the decommissioned DIMM1 Seeing Monitor. *Credit: CTIO/NOIRLab/NSF/AURA/B. Tafreshi*